

significant association of rs1800625 and rs184003 polymorphisms with the Breast cancer risk in a recessive genotype model: an integrated expression, ceRNA and SNP investigation

Forough Moradi¹, Parisa Mohamadynejad^{1*}

1 Department of biology, faculty of sciences, Shahrekord Branch, Islamic Azad University, Shahrekord, Iran.

*Corresponding Author

Parisa Mohamadynejad (p.mohammadi@iaushk.ac.ir)

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Abstract

Background:

Background: Breast cancer is one of the important health problems in the worldwide. Differences in the gene expression and the sequence of the gene and RNAs could have a significant effect on Breast cancer development and pathogenicity.

Method: Microarray data analysis was performed to evaluate the AGER expression in BC samples. An integrated ceRNA network was performed to find the related miRNAs and lncRNAs to AGER and visualized by Cytoscape. HRM real-time PCR experiment was performed to understand the effect of two rs1800625 and rs184003 SNPs on the Breast cancer risk.

Results: AGER have a significant down-regulation in the Breast cancer samples. An integrated ceRNA network could regulate the expression of AGER and effect on that in BC. The mutant allele of the two rs1800625 and rs184003 SNPs could have a significant effect on the risk of Breast cancer, both in recessive genotype model.

Discussion: It is highly recommended that the interaction of micro-RNAs with the rs1800652 and rs184003 and rs1800652 be analyzed for obtaining more accurate information about the impact of this gene and related polymorphisms in Breast cancer development.

Keywords: ceRNA, Single Nucleotide Polymorphism, AGER, lncRNA.

Introduction

Breast cancer is one of health problems worldwide, most common cancer second to lung cancer, and second cause of death due to cancers [27]. Factors such as genetic variations: chromosomal abnormality, epigenetics, and polymorphisms and environmental factors play a role in predisposition to breast cancer (*Cloning and expression of a cell surface receptor for advanced glycosylation end products of proteins - PubMed, no date; Harirchi et al., 2011*)[9]. Although preventive medications, chemotherapy, and surgery are available but cure of breast cancer is disappointing, as recurrence occur in most cases. Therefore, it is clinically important to identify biological biomarkers through molecular studies.

When cancer cells aggress, metastasis; expand throughout the body and induce inflammation which is immune system response. For coping with pathogens, the body has immune system including adaptive and innate immunity systems. B and T lymphocytes are of executive agents; B lymphocytes transformed to plasmalemma cells, since stimulated with antigens such as

bacteria, viruses, parasites, proteins, and polysaccharides. Plasmalemma cells produce immunoglobulins which attach and devastate pathogens. As the process repeat again and again, devastated cells sedimented and induce inflammation. Increased inflammation may result in chronic disease [19].

Immune system has effective role in prevention and treatment of cancers, as any disability in immune system could increase predisposition to disease through gene expression variations. RAGE (Receptor for advance Glycation End products) protein composed from 404 amino acids, is a transmembrane receptor, and a member of immunoglobulins family by two chains despite four light and heavy chains of immunoglobulins structure. RAGE is a multiligand, affinity to various ligands, and has remarkable importance in wide range of disease such as inflammatory disease like cancers [26].

HMGB, S100, Amyloid -protein, and advanced glycation end products (AGE) are some of RAGE ligands. Owing to ability to attach AGE products, RAGE is called AGER too. Ages are

mainly glycoproteins composed from glycans, which are formed from sugar and protein attachment through nonenzymatic Maillard reaction and will transform to stable Amadori compounds. Accumulation of Amadori could irreversibly damage body tissues [4].

Cell signaling process is based on ligand and receptor attachment, which activate intercellular signaling pathways. After attachment of AGE, RAGE causes RAS/MAPK and ERK/MEK signaling pathways cascade induction, which finally activate NF-K transcription factor.

NF-K regulate several genes involved in inflammation, in which stimulate active and prolonged immune system [21]. The above-mentioned pathways are important cell signaling pathways. The pathways play key roles in cell growth, differentiation, and migration. So, their uncontrolled activation in humans result in cancer as one third of all human cancers activated through the pathway [21]. Dysregulation of Induced immune response during tumorigenesis would act as a tumorigenesis promoter. Therefore, constitute molecular link between cancer and inflammation which would results in inflammatory response preservation and metastasis induction.

RAGE gene is sequenced by neeper et al in 1992. The gene has epistatic interaction with immune response involved genes located among major histocompatibility complex II (MHCII) tumor necrosis factor (TNF-), and HOX12 genes. RAGE is located on chromosome 6 and has 11 exons and 10 introns. RAGE has 6 isoforms in different tissues such as brain endothelial [26]. RAGE is highly expressed in fetal period in contrast to adulthood (*Survey of the distribution of a newly characterized receptor for advanced glycation end products in tissues - PubMed*, no date)[25]. In type II diabetes, Alzheimer, inflammatory disease, and cancers (except for skin and lung cancers) RAGE is considerably expressed [1].

This study aimed to compare genotypic discrimination frequencies of rs184003 and rs1800625 SNPs, which are located on intron 7 and promoter of RAGE gene respectively, in breast cancer patients with controls by Real-time HRM method. Both groups are studied from age and treatment status point of view. Also, based on bioinformatics analyses, the expression level of RAGE gene in the Breast cancer samples was analyzed. Furthermore, an integrated network analysis was performed to find a significantly ceRNA network, based of RAGE and the correlated miRNAs and lncRNAs.

Material and methods:

Microarray analysis

Microarray analysis was performed by R Studio (4.1.0) software on the GSE42568 dataset. The raw microarray data of Breast cancer samples was downloaded from GEO online database (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/>) by *GEOquery* [22] package. Differential expression analysis (DEG) of the GSE42568 was performed by *limma* [20] package. The *GEOquery* and *limma* packages were obtained from *Bioconductor* database (<https://www.bioconductor.org/>). Normalization of the raw data was performed by Quantile normalization method. The plots and figures were figured by *ggplot2* and *heatmap* packages, downloaded from CRAN (<https://cran.r-project.org/>). The genes with the logFC bigger than two were considered as the high expressed genes and the genes with logFC lower than -2 were considered as the down-regulated genes in this study.

Bioinformatics analyses

Protein-Protein interaction analyses was performed by *STRING* online database (<https://string-db.org/>). The miRNA-mRNA network analysis was performed by *miRWalk2* online software (<http://mirwalk.umm.uni-heidelberg.de/>). The miRNA-lncRNA interaction analysis was performed by *lncBase 3* online software (www.microrna.gr/lncBase). The ceRNA network figure was figured by the *Cytoscape 3.8.0* software. To find the relative SNP to the *RAGE* gene, the dbSNP online database was performed.

Sample preparation

Blood samples were drawn from 150 cases (after pathologic diagnosis) and 150 controls referring to Saba special clinic and Alzahra hospital (Esfahan, IRAN) via patient testimonial privilege. Then the samples incubated at -20 0C in EDTA containing tubes.

Samples DNA were extracted using Genetbio kit. Quantity and quality of extracted DNAs were assessed by agarose gel electrophoresis (1%) and Nanodrop, respectively. Real time-PCR assay was done to detect SNPs of interest using sequence specific primers (Table 2). The primers were designed via online software in NCBI.

Table 1. The primer sequence table.

Gene	Polymorphism	The sequence	Size, nt
RAGE	rs1822625 F	GGGGCAGTTCTCTCCTCACT	20
	rs1822625 F	AAGGCTCCCCAACAGGAC	18
	rs184003 R	GCCAGAAGGTGGAGCACTAG	20
	rs184003 R	ACCCTCTTCTCCTCCTCAGC	20

Real-time PCR HRM analysis

Real time-PCR and HRM analysis were done using solis Bio Dyne master mix. The total volume of reaction mixture was 1 μ l contained 0.2 μ l of each forward and reverse primers, 1 μ l of DNA, and 6.6 μ l of H₂O. Real time-PCR and HRM analysis were done using Rotorgene 6000 thermocycler as described in Table 3. Specificity of primers were confirmed by melting curves analysis provided by real time-PCR machine.

4.5. Statistical analyses

For analyzing the genotype frequency of polymorphisms, the SPSS (26) was performed. The frequency graphs were performed by Graph Pad Prism 8. The chi-square test was performed to analyze the frequency of genotypes. The significance level of this

study was 0.05. The odd ratio was demonstrated by logistic regression in SPSS.

Results

Bioinformatics analyses

Microarray analysis of the GSE42568 dataset revealed was performed (Figure 1). 104 Breast cancer samples and 17 control samples were analyzed. After normalization and quality control of samples, the DEG analysis was performed (Figure 2). This analysis revealed that the RAGE gene have a significant down-regulation in Breast cancer samples (logFC = -2.4, adj. P. Value = 0.0005, Figure 3). Based on these analyses, the RAGE gene was selected for the next investigations.

Figure 1. The Pearson correlation heatmap of GSE42568 microarray samples

Figure 2: Principal component analysis of GSE42568 samples.

Figure 3: Volcano plot of differentially expressed genes of the GSE42568 tumor samples, compared to control samples. $\logFC > 2$ and < -2 was considered as the threshold of expression. *RAGE* is indicating by a black point in the plot.

The protein-protein interaction analysis was performed by STRING online software. Based on this analysis, the *RAGE*

(*AGER*) protein is in interaction with the proteins represented in the Figure 4.

Figure 4: The STRING protein-protein interaction analysis.

The miRNA-mRNA-lncRNA (ceRNA) interaction analysis was performed by miRWalk 2 and lncBase 3 online software. Based on this analysis, an integrated ceRNA network was found and

visualized (Figure 5). The correlated miRNA and lncRNA is indicating in table 2.

Table 2: The miRNAs and lncRNAs, correlated to each other.

Genes	miRNAs	lncRNAs - has-miR-15a-3p
	hsa-miR-15a-3p	XIST
	hsa-miR-19b-1-5p	USP27X-AS1
	hsa-miR-21-3p	TUG1
	hsa-miR-22-3p	TP73-AS1
	hsa-miR-23a-5p	PVT1
	hsa-miR-92a-3p	PTOV1-AS2
	hsa-miR-92a-2-5p	PSMA3-AS1
RAGE	hsa-miR-103a-3p	
	hsa-miR-105-3p	
	hsa-miR-107	
	hsa-miR-197-5p	
	hsa-miR-30c-2-3p	
	hsa-miR-139-3p	
	hsa-miR-204-5p	
	hsa-miR-211-5p	
	hsa-miR-211-3p	
	hsa-miR-212-5p	
	hsa-miR-214-3p	
	hsa-miR-221-3p	
	hsa-miR-224-5p	

Figure 5: The ceRNA network, correlated to AGER gene.

Based on the dbSNP database, we demonstrated that the two rs1800625 and rs184003 single nucleotide polymorphisms that could have a significant effect on the expression level of AGER and the pathogenicity of this gene. So, these two SNP were selected for experimental investigations.

**Genotype distribution analyses
Rs184003**

It is demonstrated that the T allele as the mutant allele and the TT genotype of rs184003 was significantly associated with the Breast cancer (Table 3, Figure 6).

Table 3: AGER rs184003 allele and genotype distribution in Breast cancer patient, control samples and total population.

		Group			P	
		Case	Control	Total		
Genotype	GG	Count	46	72	118	0.029
		%	39.00%	61.00%	100.00%	
	TG	Count	68	80	148	
		%	45.90%	54.10%	100.00%	
	TT	Count	22	12	34	
		%	64.70%	35.30%	100.00%	
Total	Count	136	164	300		
	%	45.30%	54.70%	100.00%		
Allele	G	Count	160	224	384	0.016
		%	41.70%	58.30%	100.00%	
	T	Count	112	104	216	
		%	51.90%	48.10%	100.00%	
Total	Count	272	328	600		
	%	45.30%	54.70%	100.00%		

As indicated in Table 3, the most frequent allele in the tumor and control samples and also in total population was allele G (160, 244, and 384). But the frequency of allele T in case samples was higher than control individual (51.90 vs. 48.10%, P. Value: 0.016). Genotype frequency of this study revealed that the heterozygous TT was the most frequent genotype among all the control, case and population samples (68, 80, and 148). But according to statistical analysis, the homozygous TT genotype frequency was significantly high in the Breast cancer samples, compared to control (64.7 and 35.3 %, P. Value: 0.029).

The association of the genotype frequency of rs184003 is showing by Table 4. Allele comparison revealed that the mutant T allele was significantly correlated with the higher risk of Breast cancer development (OR: 1.508, P. Value: 0.016). Also, comparing the genotypes distribution in different genotype models (Dominant, recessive, and co-dominant) revealed that the T allele could have the more severe effect on the Breast cancer development, up to 5.145 folds (P. Value: 0.016). Furthermore, it was demonstrated that the co-dominant model (TG genotype) had no relation with the risk of BC (P. Value: 0.833).

Table 4: Correlation of the alleles and genotypes of rs184003 with the risk of BC.

	Model	P. Value	OR	95% CI	
				Lower	Upper
Allele	T / G	0.016	1.508	1.078	2.108
Dominant	TT + TG / GG	0.075	1.531	0.957	2.451
Recessive	TT / TG + GG	0.016	2.444	1.161	5.145
Co-dominant	TG / TT + GG	0.833	1.05	0.666	1.654

Figure 6: Allele and genotype frequency of the rs184003.

Rs1800625

Genotype and allele frequency distribution of rs1800625 is showing by Table 5.

Table 5: Genotype distribution of rs1800625 alleles.

			Group			P
			Case	Control	Total	
Genotype	CC	Count	14	2	16	0.007
		%	87.50%	12.50%	100.00%	
	TC	Count	24	30	54	
		%	44.40%	55.60%	100.00%	
	TT	Count	112	118	230	
		%	48.70%	51.30%	100.00%	
Total	Count	150	150	300		
	%	50.00%	50.00%	100.00%		
Allele	C	Count	52	34	86	0.036
		%	60.50%	39.50%	100.00%	
	T	Count	248	266	514	
		%	48.20%	51.80%	100.00%	
Total	Count	300	300	600		
	%	50.00%	50.00%	100.00%		

As indicating in the Table 5, the wild T allele is the most frequented allele in both control and case groups (266 and 248). But according to statistical analyses, frequency of the mutant C allele was significantly higher in the breast cancer samples, compared to control individuals (60.5 vs. 39.5%, P. Value: 0.036). Also, genotype frequency analysis was revealed that the homozygous CC genotype was significantly higher in the case samples, compared to control (87.5 vs. 12.5%, P. Value: 0.007).

Association of the rs1800625 alleles and genotypes is indicating by Table 6. The Mutant C allele have a significant positive association with the breast cancer development (OR: 1.64, P. Value: 0.036). Also, the C allele could have a significant positive effect on the BC development, in a recessive genotype model (OR: 7.618, P. Value: 0.002). The allele and genotype frequency of rs1800625 is indicating by Figure 7.

Table 6: Association of alleles and genotypes of rs1800625 with BC development.

	Model	P. Value	OR	95% CI	
				Lower	Upper
	C / T	0.036	1.64	1.03	2.613
Dominant	CC + CT / TT	0.413	1.251	0.732	2.14
Recessive	CC / CT + TT	0.002	7.618	1.7	34.132
Co-dominant	CT / CC + TT	0.367	0.762	0.421	1.377

Figure 7: Genotype and allele frequency of rs1800625 in Breast cancer samples.

Discussion

To obtaining an integrated and reliable results about the differences in the gene expressions, RNA interactions and single nucleotide polymorphisms, at the beginning we performed an integrated bioinformatics analyses, including microarray data analysis, protein-protein interaction, and ceRNA network analysis. Based on this analysis, first of all, we demonstrated that AGER could have a significant change in the expression level at the Breast cancer tissues, comparing to control individuals. Thus, we performed and miRNA-mRNA interaction analysis to find possible miRNAs that could be effective of the AGER expression level. Then, a lncRNA-miRNA analysis was performed to understand the possible ceRNA network and significant mRNA-miRNA-lncRNA axis that could be effective on the Breast cancer development. We demonstrated that hsa-miR-15a-3p could have more significantly high scored interaction with AGER. Previous studies have been discussed about the possible role of hsa-miR-15a-3p on the mouse cancer cells and apoptosis in human cancer cell lines [6]. Also, previous studies revealed that miR-15a could enhance the anticancer effect of cisplatin in resistant of non-small cell lung cancer cells [2]. However, the main role and mechanism of this miRNA effect on the Breast cancer development is already unclear. It is suggested that the experimental analyses be performed on the expression level of hsa-miR-15a-3p as a possible biomarker for Breast cancer. The interaction of this micro-RNA and AGER also could be investigated experimentally. Furthermore, by ceRNA interaction analysis, we demonstrated that XIST, USP27X-AS1, TUG1, TP73-AS1, PVT1, PTOV1-AS2 and PSMA3-AS1 lncRNAs could have a significant interaction with hsa-miR-15a-3p. So, these long non-

coding RNAs could have a biological competition with the AGER gene, for binding to hsa-miR-15a-3p. It is highly recommended that the expression level and interaction of the following lncRNAs will be investigated in BC patient. About lncRNA XIST, several studies have been discussed about the roles of it in various cancer types. For example, D Chen et al. revealed that XIST could expedite metastasis in the colorectal cancer cells [3]. Also, XIST reduction in BC could upregulate AKT phosphorylation by repress the expression of PHLPP1 [12]. Previous studies also revealed that lncRNA TUG1 could have a prognostic role for BC outcome [18]. This non-coding RNA have essential roles in migration, apoptosis and proliferation of cancer cells [18]. Also, TUG1 mediates methotrexate resistance in the Colorectal cancer in a miR-186/CPEB2 ceRNA axis [16]. Up-regulation of this lncRNA could enhance the migration of cervical cancer cells [11]. About lncRNA PVT1, previous studies revealed that this lncRNA could have an essential role in the cancer development [5] and cancer treatment [17], including Breast cancer [8]. Despite the extensive researches about the molecular mechanisms of these coding and non-coding RNAs, the main characteristics and roles of these RNAs in different human pathological conditions is still unknown. So, it is highly recommended that the interaction and expression of the following RNAs be investigate to obtaining reliable information and help cancer treatment and prognosis.

Our bioinformatics analyses have an integrated result about the expression, interaction and the effect of coding and non-coding RNAs in cancer development. Furthermore, we select he two novel single nucleotide polymorphisms on the RAGE gene that selected from microarray analysis and performed an HRM

experiment to investigate about the role of this SNP on Breast cancer development. According to our experiment, both SNPs have significant effect of the BC pathogenicity and could increase the risk of BC in patients. About rs1800625, previous studies also reported the role of this SNP on Gastric cancer [10], Hepatocellular carcinoma [24], and also Breast cancer [7]. Also, about rs184003, previous studies have been demonstrated that this SNP could regulate the RAGE expression in cervical cancer [15], urothelial cell carcinoma [13], and oral cancer [23]. It is highly suggested that the interaction of micro-RNAs with the rs184003 and rs1800625 regions of AGER mRNA be perform to obtain more accurate information about the mechanism of this

Conclusion

In this integrated study, it has been demonstrated that AGER have a significant difference in the expression level of Breast cancer patient, comparing to control individuals. Also, the correlated miRNA and lncRNAs could have positive or negative effects on the expression level of AGER. Finally, we experimentally understand that the two rs184003 and rs1800625 SNPs could have a significant effect on the risk of Breast cancer disease.

Abbreviations

BC: Breast Cancer
GEO: Gene Expression Omnibus
Adj. P. Value: Adjusted P. Value
PCR: Polymerase Chain Reaction

References

- [1] Barnes, M. R. (2010) 'Genetic variation analysis for biomedical researchers: A primer', *Methods in Molecular Biology*. Humana Press Inc., pp. 1–20. doi: 10.1007/978-1-60327-367-1_1.
- [2] Bozok Çetintaş, V. *et al.* (2016) 'miR-15a enhances the anticancer effects of cisplatin in the resistant non-small cell lung cancer cells', *Tumor Biology*, 37(2), pp. 1739–1751. doi: 10.1007/s13277-015-3950-9.
- [3] Chen, D. L. *et al.* (2017) 'Long noncoding rna xist expedites metastasis and modulates epithelial–mesenchymal transition in colorectal cancer', *Cell Death and Disease*, 8(8), p. 3011. doi: 10.1038/cddis.2017.421.
- [4] *Cloning and expression of a cell surface receptor for advanced glycosylation end products of proteins - PubMed* (no date). Available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/1378843/> (Accessed: 28 June 2021).
- [5] Cui, M. *et al.* (2016) 'Long non-coding RNA PVT1 and cancer', *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communications*. Academic Press Inc., pp. 10–14. doi: 10.1016/j.bbrc.2015.12.101.
- [6] Druz, A. *et al.* (2013) 'Large-scale screening identifies a novel microRNA, miR-15a-3p, which induces apoptosis in human cancer cell lines', *RNA Biology*, 10(2), pp. 287–300. doi: 10.4161/ma.23339.
- [7] Ghafouri-Fard, S. *et al.* (2019) 'Association analysis between genomic variants within advanced glycation end product specific receptor (AGER) gene and risk of breast cancer in Iranian women', *Heliyon*, 5(10). doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2019.e02542.
- [8] Guan, Y. *et al.* (2007) 'Amplification of PVT1 contributes to the pathophysiology of ovarian and breast cancer', *Clinical Cancer Research*, 13(19), pp. 5745–5755. doi: 10.1158/1078-0432.CCR-06-2882.
- [9] Harirchi, I. *et al.* (2011) 'Twenty years of breast cancer in Iran: Downstaging without a formal screening program', *Annals of Oncology*, 22(1), pp. 93–97. doi: 10.1093/annonc/mdq303.
- [10] Hu, D. *et al.* (2019) 'Association of RAGE gene four single nucleotide polymorphisms with the risk, invasion, metastasis and overall survival of gastric cancer in Chinese', *Journal of Cancer*, 10(2), pp. 504–509. doi: 10.7150/jca.26583.
- [11] Hu, Y. *et al.* (2017) 'Upregulation of long noncoding RNA TUG1 promotes cervical cancer cell proliferation and migration', *Cancer Medicine*, 6(2), pp. 471–482. doi: 10.1002/cam4.994.
- [12] Huang, Y. S. *et al.* (2016) 'Xist reduction in breast cancer upregulates AKT phosphorylation via HDAC3-mediated repression of PHLPP1 expression', *Oncotarget*, 7(28), pp. 43256–43266. doi: 10.18632/oncotarget.9673.
- [13] Hung, S. C. *et al.* (2019) 'Impact of RAGE polymorphisms on urothelial cell carcinoma clinicopathologic characteristics and long-term survival', *Urologic Oncology: Seminars and Original Investigations*, 37(9), pp. 573.e9–573.e17. doi: 10.1016/j.urolonc.2019.02.012.

DEG: Differentially Expressed Gene
SNP: Single Nucleotide Polymorphism
mi RNA: Micro-RNA

Declaration

Consent for publication: Not applicable.

Availability of data and materials: The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Competing interests: The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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Authors' contributions: FM performed the experiments, data analysis, and visualization. PM and MS have revised the manuscript and validated the experiment. PM is the corresponding author of this manuscript.

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- [14] Kalea, A. Z. *et al.* (2010) 'Alternatively sliced RAGEv1 inhibits tumorigenesis through suppression of JNK signaling', *Cancer Research*, 70(13), pp. 5628–5638. doi: 10.1158/0008-5472.CAN-10-0595.
- [15] Lee, C. Y. *et al.* (2018) 'Impact of the receptor for advanced glycation end products genetic polymorphisms on the progression in uterine cervical cancer', *Journal of Cancer*, 9(21), pp. 3886–3893. doi: 10.7150/jca.27960.
- [16] Li, C. *et al.* (2017) 'TUG1 mediates methotrexate resistance in colorectal cancer via miR-186/CPEB2 axis', *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communications*, 491(2), pp. 552–557. doi: 10.1016/j.bbrc.2017.03.042.
- [17] Li, M. Y. *et al.* (2019) 'Regulatory mechanisms and clinical applications of the long non-coding RNA PVT1 in cancer treatment', *Frontiers in Oncology*. Frontiers Media S.A. doi: 10.3389/fonc.2019.00787.
- [18] Liu, J. *et al.* (2017) 'Prognostic role of lncRNA TUG1 for cancer outcome: Evidence from 840 cancer patients', *Oncotarget*, 8(30), pp. 50051–50060. doi: 10.18632/oncotarget.17844.
- [19] Loose, D. and Van De Wiele, C. (2009) 'The immune system and cancer', *Cancer Biotherapy and Radiopharmaceuticals*. Mary Ann Liebert, Inc. 140 Huguenot Street, 3rd Floor New Rochelle, NY 10801 USA , pp. 369–376. doi: 10.1089/cbr.2008.0593.
- [20] Ritchie, M. E. *et al.* (2015) 'Limma powers differential expression analyses for RNA-sequencing and microarray studies', *Nucleic Acids Research*, 43(7), p. e47. doi: 10.1093/nar/gkv007.
- [21] Schmidt, A. M. *et al.* (2001) 'The multiligand receptor RAGE as a progression factor amplifying immune and inflammatory responses', *Journal of Clinical Investigation*, 108(7), pp. 949–955. doi: 10.1172/jci14002.
- [22] Sean, D. and Meltzer, P. S. (2007) 'GEOquery: A bridge between the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) and BioConductor', *Bioinformatics*, 23(14), pp. 1846–1847. doi: 10.1093/bioinformatics/btm254.
- [23] Su, S. *et al.* (2015) 'RAGE gene polymorphism and environmental factor in the risk of oral cancer', *Journal of Dental Research*, 94(3), pp. 403–411. doi: 10.1177/0022034514566215.
- [24] Su, S. C. *et al.* (2015) 'Effects of RAGE Gene Polymorphisms on the Risk and Progression of Hepatocellular Carcinoma', *Medicine (United States)*, 94(34), p. e1396. doi: 10.1097/MD.0000000000001396.
- [25] *Survey of the distribution of a newly characterized receptor for advanced glycation end products in tissues - PubMed* (no date). Available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/8256857/> (Accessed: 28 June 2021).
- [26] Tesařová, P. *et al.* (2007) 'Receptor for advanced glycation end products (RAGE) - Soluble form (sRAGE) and gene polymorphisms in patients with breast cancer', *Cancer Investigation*, 25(8), pp. 720–725. doi: 10.1080/07357900701560521.
- [27] Warburton, A. J. and Boone, D. N. (2017) 'Insights from Global Analyses of Long Noncoding RNAs in Breast Cancer', *Current Pathobiology Reports*. Springer, pp. 23–34. doi: 10.1007/s40139-017-0122-1.